

Typhus Group Rickettsiosis and the Dengue Diagnostic Paradox: Low Laboratory-Confirmed Dengue Amid the Americas' Largest Epidemic

EMERGING INFECTIOUS DISEASES NETWORK LETTER

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ABSTRACT

Rickettsial diseases, particularly typhus group rickettsioses, remain underrecognized across the Americas. South Texas data reveal persistent murine typhus, mirroring Central American ecological and socioeconomic conditions. Amid low laboratory-confirmed dengue (~11%), many dengue-like febrile illnesses may represent unrecognized rickettsioses, signaling the need for a paradigm shift in surveillance, diagnostics, and clinical awareness.

NETWORK LETTER

Rickettsial diseases remain an underrecognized and neglected component of emerging infectious threats throughout the Americas, despite their historical presence and substantial potential to cause morbidity in tropical and subtropical settings. The comprehensive 18-year review of murine typhus in South Texas conducted by Howard and Fergie [1] offers valuable insights into the epidemiologic patterns, clinical manifestations, and public health implications of *Rickettsia typhi* infections among pediatric populations. Their work highlights a persistent endemic focus embedded within ecological and socioeconomic contexts that closely mirror those of Central America—particularly along the Pacific and Atlantic lowlands of Honduras, El Salvador, Nicaragua, and Costa Rica. These parallels warrant renewed regional attention to diagnostic, surveillance, and vector control deficiencies. When these observations are viewed alongside the strikingly low dengue test positivity rate – only 11%, as shown in Table 1 – they prompt a serious question. Are these clinically diagnosed dengue cases truly dengue, or could a clinically similar febrile illness be masquerading as a dengue-like syndrome without laboratory confirmation? An anomaly of this magnitude warrants careful investigation rather than passive acceptance.

Murine typhus, caused by *R. typhi* and transmitted primarily by the cat flea (*Ctenocephalides felis*) and the oriental rat flea (*Xenopsylla cheopis*), represents a classic flea-borne zoonosis whose incidence reflects interactions between urbanization, vector ecology, and socioeconomic vulnerability [2–3]. Historically endemic to coastal areas of the southeastern United States during the early to mid-20th century [4], its reemergence in South Texas [1] and sporadic detection in California [5] underscore the continuity of an eco-epidemiological corridor that extends into Mesoamerica. The recent identification of *R. typhi* in Costa Rica [6] and serologic evidence of exposure to spotted fever group and typhus group rickettsiae in several Central American countries [7–8] suggest ongoing, silent transmission in areas where diagnostic infrastructure is limited and surveillance remains largely passive.

Central America encompasses a range of ecological gradients—from humid tropical lowlands to semi-arid intermountain valleys—that support abundant populations of peridomestic reservoirs and vectors. The combination of urban–rural interface zones, proliferation of stray animals,

inadequate solid waste management, and climate-sensitive vector dynamics creates ideal conditions for flea-borne transmission cycles similar to those documented in South Texas [1,4,8]. Temperature, rainfall, and humidity patterns directly influence flea survival and rodent population density, while socioeconomic factors—such as informal housing, domestic animal infestation, and limited access to veterinary care—exacerbate human exposure risks [9]. These interacting determinants sustain an ecological niche highly favorable to *R. typhi* persistence, yet remain underappreciated due to limited clinical awareness and public health prioritization.

Comparable ecological and social conditions are widespread across the isthmus, where peridomestic rodents (*Rattus rattus*, *R. norvegicus*) and opossums (*Didelphis marsupialis*) serve as potential reservoirs, and *C. felis* is ubiquitous among cats and dogs. The potential for zoonotic spillover is therefore considerable, especially in peri-urban environments. Moreover, climatic disruptions—such as El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events—modulate rodent and flea populations and have been linked to increased rickettsial transmission in other endemic areas. With climate variability intensifying across Central America, these ecological interactions are expected to become more pronounced in the coming decades.

The region’s vulnerability to rickettsial diseases must also be interpreted in light of persistent health system limitations. Chronic underinvestment, weak laboratory capacity, and fragmented surveillance systems hinder early detection of emerging zoonoses. The coexistence of multiple reservoirs—rodents, opossums, and domestic animals—within densely populated human settlements further increases the probability of transmission. Poverty-driven environmental degradation and unplanned urbanization aggravate these vulnerabilities, reinforcing the need for a coordinated “One Health” approach that integrates human, veterinary, and environmental surveillance.

Despite the likely endemicity of murine typhus and related rickettsioses, most Central American countries lack reliable laboratory diagnostic capacity. National reference laboratories often rely on external confirmation through indirect immunofluorescence assays (IFA), which are costly and unavailable outside major cities. Consequently, substantial underreporting and clinical misclassification occur, as febrile illnesses consistent with rickettsial infection are frequently attributed to more common etiologies such as dengue, leptospirosis, or chikungunya. This diagnostic gap perpetuates a cycle of invisibility and delayed treatment, resulting in preventable morbidity—particularly among children.

Dengue continues to represent the foremost vector-borne disease challenge in Central America. In 2024, all four-dengue virus (DENV) serotypes were documented in circulation across the region (Table 1). A total of 536,006 suspected cases were reported, yet only 62,285 (12%) were laboratory-confirmed [10]. Current national regulations stipulate that every severe or hospitalized dengue case must have at least one blood sample collected for diagnostic confirmation. However, according to personal communications from infectious disease specialists in the region, laboratory positivity among severe cases is estimated to be approximately 50%. These findings underscore persistent gaps in diagnostic capacity and surveillance quality across Central America—gaps that call for innovative, out-of-the-box approaches to strengthen regional preparedness and response.

The South Texas experience demonstrates how consistent data collection and laboratory confirmation can elucidate disease burden and transmission dynamics. Over an 18-year period, 213 pediatric cases were confirmed, showing stable annual incidence and distinct seasonal peaks [1]. Comparable systematic surveillance is lacking in Central America, where national disease control programs predominantly focus on arboviruses and malaria, leaving rickettsioses largely unmonitored. Establishing sentinel surveillance sites, incorporating rickettsial testing into febrile illness algorithms, and expanding physician training are critical steps forward. Regional reference laboratories, under the coordination of the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO), could play a pivotal role in standardizing diagnostic procedures and building workforce capacity.

Findings from South Texas also highlight the benefits of early doxycycline administration and heightened clinician awareness. In that cohort, prompt initiation of therapy correlated with shorter hospital stays and fewer complications [1]. In contrast, empirical doxycycline use for undifferentiated febrile illness in resource-limited Central American settings is often constrained by diagnostic uncertainty and antimicrobial stewardship concerns [11]. Developing clinical algorithms that integrate epidemiologic risk factors and local vector data could help reconcile these tensions, ensuring timely treatment while preserving rational antibiotic use. Pediatricians, in particular, should maintain a high index of suspicion for rickettsial disease during warm and rainy months when vector activity peaks.

R. typhi infection in adults can produce a wider and more severe spectrum of complications than historically appreciated. In addition to the classic febrile illness, adults may display significant organ involvement including acute kidney injury, hepatitis, pneumonitis, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) when infection progresses unrecognized. [12–14]. Central nervous system involvement is especially important, with documented meningitis, meningoencephalitis, cranial neuropathies, and prolonged post-infectious headaches [12,15,16]. Although most clinical and laboratory features fail to distinguish between typhus and viral pathogens, certain findings can point an attentive clinician toward the correct diagnosis. Hypoglycorrhachia, reported in up to 38% of typhus group rickettsial CNS infections, in the context of mild to moderate hyperproteinorrhachia and pleocytosis; paired with an otherwise unremarkable neuroimaging test, remains one of the most informative early laboratory clues, helping distinguish these cases from more common viral etiologies [13,15,17]. Delayed diagnosis is strongly associated with worsened outcomes, as untreated or late-treated adult cases demonstrate higher rates of neurological sequelae and significantly increased mortality – rising from ~0.4% in uncomplicated infections to as high as 27% when CNS disease is present [12,13]. These findings reiterate the importance of early clinical suspicion and rapid initiation of doxycycline to prevent progression to severe multisystem involvement.

Madril *et al.*, in a concise but consequential 2025 communication [18], raised an alarm by documenting seven adult cases of typhus group rickettsia CNS infection, including four confirmed and three probable. This represents the largest single-region cohort yet described in the English-language literature. One of the most striking aspects of the report is the authors' candor that these cases were only recognized through time, accumulated experience, and a deliberate shift toward routinely including typhus in the daily differential diagnosis. The message

is unmistakable: there is a learning curve for every clinician, but the first step is abandoning the deeply ingrained perception that typhus is an exotic rarity. Recognition increases case discovery, and case discovery sharpens clinical acumen – eventually reaching a tipping point where the disease is not an afterthought but a permanent fixture in diagnostic reasoning. Madril *et al.*, argue that they have reached “the end of the beginning”, the threshold at which a once “rare” disease reveals itself to be surprisingly common. Their observation is reinforced by statewide data showing typhus now accounts for 57% of all vector-borne infections in Texas.[15]

The group also underscores how difficult true case capture remains [18]. Without point-of-care testing, with consent barriers, family contact challenges, and layers of bureaucratic obstruction, the seven reported cases may represent only a fraction of the true burden. Yet the authors do maintain some amount of cautious optimism. They argue that this moment should mark the end of dismissing typhus as rare, the end of its absence from medical school curricula, and the end of its status as an overlooked, “orphaned” pathogen – with renewed urgency to develop reliable diagnostics by both public and private sectors. Only with that mindset can the pattern observed in Texas be recognized across Central America. When that transition occurs, the large proportion of cases currently attributed to dengue without confirmatory testing may finally shrink, and the longstanding diagnostic gap may reveal its true name: *Rickettsia Typhus Group*

Future priorities for research and policy include: (1) molecular characterization of *R. typhi* and other rickettsiae in vectors and reservoirs; (2) seroepidemiologic studies among high-risk populations; (3) incorporation of rickettsial diagnostics into national febrile surveillance frameworks; and (4) evaluation of climate–vector–host interactions. Collaborative partnerships among universities, ministries of health, and international entities—such as the U.S. CDC Rickettsial Zoonoses Branch and PAHO’s regional zoonoses program—will be essential for advancing technical capacity and regional data harmonization. Concurrently, community-level interventions to reduce flea infestations in domestic animals and improve environmental sanitation can help interrupt transmission cycles.

Central America’s experiences with other reemerging infections—dengue, chikungunya, Zika, and leptospirosis—demonstrate that reactive surveillance is insufficient to protect vulnerable populations. Rickettsial diseases demand a proactive, multisectoral strategy grounded in cross-border collaboration, diagnostic readiness, and ecological understanding. The reemergence of murine typhus in Texas and its recent detection in Costa Rica are not isolated events but rather sentinel indicators of a broader regional susceptibility shaped by environmental and socioeconomic convergence. Integrating rickettsial surveillance into the regional agenda for emerging infections should therefore be considered a public health priority.

In summary, the parallels between South Texas and Central America extend beyond shared climatic and ecological features to encompass structural determinants of health vulnerability. Without enhanced diagnostic and surveillance capacity, rickettsioses will remain underrecognized, perpetuating avoidable morbidity. The work by Howard and Fergie [1] exemplifies how systematic pediatric surveillance can uncover hidden endemicity and guide targeted interventions. Adapting such frameworks for Central America represents a critical step

toward regional and global health security.

Respectfully submitted,

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Table 1. Dengue cases in Central America during 2024 [10]

Countries	Dengue Cases			Proportion of Severe Dengue *	Deaths	Dengue case fatality rate **
	Reported	Diagnosed by Laboratory	Severe Dengue			
Costa Rica	31,259	1,301	-	-	7	22.4
El Salvador	8,552	764	29	339	9	105.2
Belize	1,148	791	4	348	0	-
Guatemala	188,585	6,009	254	135	188	99.7
Honduras	177,209	10,008	2,250	1,270	160	90.3
Nicaragua	92,022	11,335	16	17	1	1.1
Panamá	37,231	32,077	330	886	52	139.7
Total	536,006	62,285	2,883			

Most dengue cases are clinically diagnosed; laboratory confirmation is low across the region (11%)

* Proportion of severe dengue cases among all dengue cases x 100,000

** Proportion of dengue deaths among all dengue cases x 100,000

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